

Stigmergic Feedback in Swarmalator Mixtures: Phase-Mediated Segregation Under Confinement

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Abstract

In this study, we explore self-organization in a two-dimensional swarm model composed of two distinct swarmalator types (A and B) with opposing angular velocities, focusing on the roles of stigmergy-mediated interactions, phase-dependent motion, and physical constraints, including boundary conditions and barrier effects. Unlike traditional approaches that rely on local or direct physical interactions, the proposed swarm coordinates through internal phase-based dynamics coupled with environmental phase modifications. The intrinsic angular velocity of each swarmalator determines its phase rotation, which in turn governs its orbital motion and phase interactions with the environment. The non-equilibrium simulations reveal varying degrees of segregation across different segregation stages, observed across different time horizons, which are quantified by pairwise measures of neighborhood homogeneity specific to swarmalator type (A or B). Co-rotating pairs (AA or BB) channel trajectories via stigmergy, forming uniform clusters of the same type. In contrast, counter-rotating pairs (AB or BA) induce phase mixing, cluster decay, and fluctuations at cluster peripheries. At high stigmergy-mediated coupling, dynamic ring-shaped clusters emerge, with their macroscopic rotation direction determined by the sign of the angular velocity. Our findings underscore the importance of the interplay between indirect interactions and spatial constraints in shaping emergent self-organized patterns. This work provides a blueprint for constructing bioinspired robotic systems that adapt through environmental feedback, paving the way for advanced environments designed to actively guide swarm behaviors.

I. INTRODUCTION

Active matter systems, composed of self-propelled particles, spontaneously self-organize, exhibiting emergent collective behaviors beyond equilibrium thermodynamics [1]. Foundational work in this field has largely focused on local interaction paradigms, where coordination arises from immediate spatial proximity. Bird flocks and fish schools serve as canonical examples. Here, alignment rules [2, 3] or topological neighbor selection, such as fixed-number coordination with six nearest particles [4], drive synchronized motion through short-range forces. These models have established that spatially confined interactions—whether metric (distance-based) or topological (number-based)—are sufficient to generate order through self-amplifying feedback loops [4–6]. Similarly, bacterial colonies and cellular aggregates form through physical interactions [7], further emphasizing the dominance of local rules in classical frameworks.

However, advances in experimental and theoretical methods have exposed the limitations of purely local frameworks. Modern studies increasingly highlight nonlocal interaction mechanisms. For instance, hydrodynamic coupling [8] induces collective vortex dynamics through long-range flows. Substrate elasticity [9] enables ultra-long-range force transmission in hybrid active-passive media. Furthermore, dynamic cluster formation in active colloids [10], where aggregation-fragmentation cycles reveal emergent nonlocal stress fields, also demonstrates these mechanisms. Stigmergy-mediated communication [11] similarly illustrates how

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microrobotic collectives adaptively modify their environment. Synthetic acoustic microrobotic swarms achieve nonlocal coordination via tunable acoustic streaming strength [12]. This shift underscores the necessity of theoretical frameworks that reconcile rule-based local coordination with field-mediated nonlocal physics, a principle highlighted by the emergent collective dynamics observed in concentration-varied robotic systems [13].

Stigmergy, a coordination mechanism where agents modify their environment to communicate indirectly, was first extensively studied in social insects like ants and termites. It plays a crucial role in behaviors such as nest building, foraging, and collective problem-solving, offering insights into how such mechanisms function in natural systems. By depositing chemical signals or other cues, organisms and entities coordinate their actions without direct interaction, leading to the emergence of complex structures and collective dynamics across multiple levels [14, 15]. In biological systems like tissue engineering, spatial organization often relies on environmental cues. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, for example, produces exopolysaccharides (EPS) that modify their surroundings to guide biofilm development and cell movement. Specifically, the EPS component Psl enhances surface attachment and biofilm stability, while the lectin LecB binds EPS to form a robust matrix [16–18]. Such EPS-mediated changes demonstrate stigmergy, as described by [19, 20], where indirect environmental alterations coordinate collective behavior.

In the animal kingdom, species often rely on indirect communication to organize and regulate behavior. Territoriality, for instance, emerges through environmental markers used to define boundaries, guiding the movement and interactions of species [21]. Such behaviors are not limited to territoriality but extend to the spread of pathogens, where stigmergy influences both the distribution and movement patterns of organisms [22]. Notably, research has shown that territorial patterns can develop from avoidance behaviors alone, without direct attractive forces [23], emphasizing the role of indirect interactions in shaping these dynamics. Although stigmergy is well-studied in natural systems, its application in artificial systems remains underexplored, enabling the design of self-organizing systems for swarm robotics and material science applications.

This work assesses whether territoriality and segregation can emerge in swarmalators [24], examining how self-propelled motion, state-dependent markings, and environmental feedback contribute to the formation of distinct groups within the swarm.

Beyond biology, stigmergy plays a pivotal role in swarm robotics and multi-agent systems, enabling the emergence of collective behaviors through local interactions, without the need for direct communication between agents [25–29]. It also underpins decision-making processes in domains such as the semantic web [30] and is harnessed by mobile microrobots to coordinate actions through modifications to their environment [11]. These applications demonstrate stigmergy’s potential to inform the design of swarmalator systems with emergent functionalities.

Self-organization in swarm systems arises from varied interaction rules, from evolutionary adaptation in biological systems [31] to state-dependent phase coupling in swarmalator models [24, 32]. Though these operate at different scales, they share a core principle: local interactions drive coordinated collective behavior. Recent studies have shown that higher-order interactions [33] and temporal delays [34] trigger distinct state transitions, accounting

for phenomena such as boundary effects and pseudo-crystalline ordering [24].

In chiral swarmalator systems, diverse behaviors—such as circular motion, clustering, and swarming—arise from intrinsic particle properties and spatial heterogeneities [35, 36]. External constraints, including pinning [37] or driven motion [38], have been studied in swarmalator models as ways to influence pattern formation, but they impose fixed spatial structure or directional bias. In contrast, chiral swarmalators generate coordination internally through local coupling and self-rotation. Other swarmalator studies have explored effects such as motility-induced phase separation [39], geometric confinement [41], long-range interactions [40], or heterogeneity in intrinsic properties [42].

This work examines the role of a stigmergy variant in governing the phase-driven motion of 2D swarmalators, characterized as chiral active matter particles. While most swarmalator models assume identical agents, recent work shows that chirality and non-uniformity yield greater diversity in collective behaviors [35]. We propose that the internal phase state of each swarmalator—defined by its velocity vector’s angular orientation—couples via stigmergy-mediated interactions. Specifically, each swarmalator deposits phase information at its current lattice node and senses neighboring node states.

We analyze non-equilibrium statistics governing two intermingled swarmalator groups with imposed co-rotating and counter-rotating phase velocities, elucidating their segregation dynamics. Our focus lies in using non-equilibrium statistics to quantify how stigmergy-mediated phase interactions lead to segregation patterns in co-rotating and counter-rotating swarmalator groups.

This research advances understanding of active swarm systems by demonstrating how non-equilibrium conditions drive segregation, akin to bidisperse systems [43] where phase separation occurs spontaneously without adhesive forces. Like oil-water partitioning, mobility-induced segregation [44, 45] contributes these dynamics, revealing that motion modes heterogeneity alone can split systems into density-distinct domains.

We propose that phase-coupled environmental feedback significantly influences swarm behavior, particularly in driving segregation. To capture these effects, our model prioritizes a combination of elementary collision dynamics and stigmergy over the explicit adhesive forces. The investigation will encompass the analysis of how curved trajectories and boundary conditions shape swarm behavior [13, 43, 44, 46]. The integration of the chiral nature of swarm motion and environmental effects has been demonstrated to reduce reliance on individual swarmalator intelligence and exhaustive communication. This approach, driven by stigmergy, aligns with the objectives of swarm robotics. For instance, Bettstetter et al. [47] have demonstrated the resource efficiency of stochastic coupling in swarmalator dynamics on robotic platforms.

The paper is structured as follows: Section II introduces the model, simulating swarmalators interacting through stigmergy on a 2D lattice. The system of differential equations governing the phase-dependent dynamics, and lattice states is outlined. Section III presents statistical measures for analyzing synchronization and collective behavior across various parameter settings, with an emphasis on the impact of a bimodal distribution of angular velocities. Section IV details the simulation results with an emphasis on the level of segregation seen via measures and particular configurations. Section V presents conclusions.

To support the explanation of the segregation mechanism, we use a simplified mean-field approximation, with details in Appendix A. Appendix B presents closed-form solutions describing phase-locked states, stability, and segregation dynamics in the two-swarmalator system coupled via a continuous stigmergic field. Appendix C shows that strong stigmergy-mediated coupling on the lattice leads to a distinctive structure in the segregation measure, with ring-shaped clusters playing a key role.

II. STIGMERGY-MEDIATED SWARMALATOR DYNAMICS IN 2D SIMULATIONS

We designed a 2D simulation model to explore how stigmergy impacts the collective behavior of chiral active matter, featuring two interacting swarmalator groups: type *A* and type *B*. Type *A* swarmalators exhibit clockwise chirality and form circular trajectories modulated by stigmergy-mediated interactions. In contrast, type *B* swarmalators display counter-clockwise chirality and produce counter-clockwise orbits.

The dynamics of both groups are driven by their internal phase states and influenced by environmental phase cues, specifically channeled trajectories. Deposited by swarmalators and their neighbors, these cues induce phase shifts that alter their movement patterns and internal phase states.

We use a discrete lattice to model stigmergic feedback via fixed environmental nodes, capturing localized, discontinuous coordination seen in biology and robotics, such as pheromone trails [48] and robotic message-passing [49]. Discretization improves efficiency by mapping agents directly to nodes, avoiding costly neighborhood searches [50] and enabling fast updates and broad parameter scans [37].

To assess if discretization captures the stigmergy-driven collective outcomes, we analyze minimal systems in continuous space: a one-agent model (Appendix A) and a two-agent system (Appendix B). The two-agent system, which self-organizes via environmental phase coupling, exhibits synchronization, phase-locking, and segregation. These are collective behaviors also predicted by the discrete model. This supports the assumption that environment-mediated coordination is robust and functions independently of geometric details, extending beyond lattice specifics. The two-agent case represents the minimalist stigmergic interaction from which all large-scale patterns in the main simulations emerge. The model’s discretization properties depend significantly on specific parameter combinations, detailed at the beginning of Section IV.

A. Swarmalator-to-node influence

Our model for stigmergy-mediated swarmalator behavior involves projecting swarmalator positions onto a lattice, facilitating crucial bidirectional feedback with environmental dynamics. Each swarmalator, indexed by i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$), is defined by its position $(x_i(t), y_i(t))$ and an internal phase $\phi_i(t)$ governing its self-propulsion. Importantly, at each time step t , interaction occurs via the four closest lattice nodes, which delineate the swarmalator’s

FIG. 1: Interaction of a swarmalator (brown, "s") with its four nearest lattice nodes (green, "n"). Lattice nodes of this elementary interaction region (indices: $\tilde{j}_{x,i}^{(1)}, \tilde{j}_{y,i}^{(1)}$, etc.) are discrete, while the swarmalator's position is continuous, scaled by the lattice spacing, ℓ_{lat} .

interaction region. Overlapping regions are observed in dense scenarios.

Fig. 1 illustrates the association of a position of a swarmalator with the lattice indices. The interaction region of a swarmalator i encompasses the four nearest lattice nodes: $(\tilde{j}_{x,i}^{(1)}, \tilde{j}_{y,i}^{(1)})$, $(\tilde{j}_{x,i}^{(2)}, \tilde{j}_{y,i}^{(1)})$, $(\tilde{j}_{x,i}^{(1)}, \tilde{j}_{y,i}^{(2)})$, and $(\tilde{j}_{x,i}^{(2)}, \tilde{j}_{y,i}^{(2)})$. Here, superscripts (1) and (2) denote the "lower" and "upper" indices along the corresponding axis. Indices $\tilde{j}_{\dots}^{(1)}$ range from 0 to $M - 1$, while indices $\tilde{j}_{\dots}^{(2)}$ range from 1 to M . The discrete node indices are determined by using the floor function. For the x coordinate, $\tilde{j}_{x,i}^{(1)} = \lfloor \frac{x_i}{\ell_{lat}} \rfloor$, where ℓ_{lat} is the lattice spacing, identifies the node to the left of the swarmalator position. The index for the right node is $\tilde{j}_{x,i}^{(2)} = \tilde{j}_{x,i}^{(1)} + 1$. Similarly, for the y coordinate, $\tilde{j}_{y,i}^{(1)} = \lfloor \frac{y_i}{\ell_{lat}} \rfloor$ and $\tilde{j}_{y,i}^{(2)} = \tilde{j}_{y,i}^{(1)} + 1$ correspond to the nodes below and above the position of the swarmalator, respectively.

The lattice node (j_x, j_y) experiences a torque, T_{n,j_x,j_y} , arising from the interaction between the swarmalator phase ϕ_i and the local phase Φ_{j_x,j_y} , and is given by

$$T_{n,j_x,j_y} = \frac{\sum_{u=1}^2 \sum_{q=1}^2 \sum_{i=1}^N \delta(\tilde{j}_{x,i}^{(u)}, j_x) \delta(\tilde{j}_{y,i}^{(q)}, j_y) \sin(\phi_i - \Phi_{j_x,j_y})}{\sum_{u'=1}^2 \sum_{q'=1}^2 \sum_{i'=1}^N \delta(\tilde{j}_{x,i'}^{(u')}, j_x) \delta(\tilde{j}_{y,i'}^{(q')}, j_y)}. \quad (1)$$

The Kronecker delta functions $\delta(\cdot, \cdot)$ ensure that only swarmalators positioned at node (j_x, j_y) contribute to the sums. The denominator counts these swarmalators, normalizing the numerator to produce the average torque exerted at the node.

1. Reflection boundary conditions and barrier-influenced conditions

The present study investigates the influence of boundary conditions on the phenomenon of bulk segregation within a two-dimensional arena $\Lambda = L \times L$ (see Fig. 2). We consider two distinct classes of boundary conditions: (i) conventional reflective boundary conditions, characterized by specular reflection of swarmalators at the perimeter of the lattice, and (ii) extended reflective barrier-influenced boundary conditions with an internal barrier. This barrier, positioned at the midpoint of one lattice wall and oriented perpendicularly to the lattice wall, has a characteristic length L_{bar} . In most cases, L_{bar} is set to $L/2$ (*Supplementary*

Material), but we generalize our investigation to cases where $L_{bar} < L$, thereby allowing the examination of barriers of varying lengths. The primary function of this internal barrier within the extended reflective barrier-influenced boundary conditions is to modify the flow of swarmalators near the square boundaries, thus enabling investigation of L_{bar} 's influence on swarm segregation [46].

FIG. 2: Schematic representation of the simulation arena Λ . (A) Basic square arena of size $L \times L$ with explicitly marked corners. (B) The same arena with the barrier of the length $L_{bar} < L$ imposed.

B. Stigmergic Influence of Neighbors

The phase dynamics of each swarmalator are influenced by local stigmergy-mediated interactions with its four nearest neighbors. The torque $T_{p,i}$ acting on swarmalator i is

$$T_{p,i} = \frac{1}{4} \sum_{u,q=1,2} \sin \left(\Phi_{\tilde{j}_{x,i}^{(u)}, \tilde{j}_{y,i}^{(q)}} - \phi_i \right). \quad (2)$$

This torque couples the swarmalator's phase ϕ_i to the phases $\tilde{\Phi}_{\tilde{j}_x^{(u)}, \tilde{j}_y^{(q)}}$ of its neighbors. The prefactor of $1/4$ accounts for the nearest neighbors. This interaction is analogous to Eq. 1.

C. Dynamics of positions, phases and lattice nodes

The system dynamics can be described by a coupled set of $3N + (M + 1)^2$ differential equations. The factor 3 stems from 2 position coordinates and 1 phase coordinate; the additional term squares the lattice degrees of freedom along one dimension. These equations describe how the phase and position variables evolve over time.

The phase at a lattice node (j_x, j_y) is denoted by $\Phi_{j_x, j_y}(t)$. The evolution of this phase is governed by the following stochastic differential equation:

$$\frac{d\Phi_{j_x, j_y}}{dt} = K_{pn} T_{n, j_x, j_y} + T_{n, st}, \quad (3)$$

where K_{pn} is the synchronization coefficient (assuming the swarmalator acts as the source of phase information recorded in the lattice), T_{n,j_x,j_y} represents the deterministic phase dynamics driven by swarmalator interactions, and $T_{n,st}$ is the stochastic term modeled as Gaussian white noise with variance $\sigma_{T_n}^2$. Thus, the phase information at each node fades over time due to stochastic noise, much like the evaporation of a pheromone trail. The influence of past interactions weakens as random fluctuations gradually erase the system's memory.

The phase ϕ_i of each swarmalator $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ evolves according to:

$$\frac{d\phi_i}{dt} = \omega_i + K_{np}T_{p,i}, \quad (4)$$

where ω_i is the intrinsic angular velocity of swarmalator i , K_{np} is the synchronization coefficient governing the transfer of torque from lattice nodes to swarmalators, and $T_{p,i}$ is the contribution of node dynamics to the swarmalator's phase evolution. The coefficients K_{pn} and K_{np} parameterize the two-way coupling between a swarmalator and a lattice node. Characterizing the distribution of intrinsic angular velocities ω_i is essential for our study to influence the system behavior.

The essential feature of a swarmalator is its phase-dependent direction of motion. Each swarmalator's internal phase, ϕ_i , dictates its direction of motion, directly influencing its velocity:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{r}_i}{dt} = k_{pp}\mathbf{F}_{pp,i} + v_{pr} \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\phi_i) \\ \sin(\phi_i) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{r}_i = (x_i, y_i)^\top$ represents the position of swarmalator i . This equation captures the coupling between phase and motion, where propulsion is directed by a swarmalator's internal phase while other forces contribute to trajectory adjustments. Specifically, it includes repulsive interactions, $k_{pp}\mathbf{F}_{pp,i}$ (scaled by the elasticity parameter k_{pp}), and a constant phase-independent propulsion speed, v_{pr} . The repulsive force, which further shapes the swarmalator's trajectory, is given by:

$$\mathbf{F}_{pp,i} = \sum_{j \neq i}^N \frac{\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j}{\ell_{pp}} \Theta(\ell_{pp} - |\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j|), \quad (6)$$

where ℓ_{pp} is the interaction threshold. The Heaviside function $\Theta(\ell_{pp} - |\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j|)$ ensures that interactions occur only within a finite range.

When the mean free path is sufficiently large that swarmalator collisions become negligible, the orbital radius $r_{p,i}$ of a single swarmalator i is given by Eq. (5):

$$r_{p,i} = \frac{v_{pr}}{|\omega_i|}. \quad (7)$$

This relationship serves as an accurate system descriptor only if stigmergy-mediated interactions (parametrized by K_{np} and K_{pn}) are much weaker than $|\omega_i|$. Additionally, geometric constraints limit its application: the lattice constant ℓ_{lat} and short-range repulsion length ℓ_{pp} constrain small-scale behavior, while the system size L limits large-scale behavior, particularly when $r_{p,i} \sim L$.

D. Swarmalator model with dual opposite angular velocities

Is it possible for territoriality or segregation to emerge from the interactions of simple agents with elementary phase-dependent internal memory, relying solely on stigmergy-mediated interactions? We investigate this using a dual-component swarmalator model version, where agent motion is governed by intrinsic phase dynamics. By introducing opposite angular velocities (ω_A and $\omega_B = -\omega_A$; $\omega_A > 0$), we hypothesize that this minimal setup could drive self-organized segregation, leading to spatial domains. We expect co-rotating swarmalators to associate, reinforcing their trajectories and forming homogeneous clusters. If confirmed, this dual-component model could shed light on how spatial patterns emerge in diverse systems. When swarmalators with opposite angular velocities interact, stigmergy-mediated interactions accompanied with collisions may disrupt trajectories, counteracting cluster formation. Additionally, the question is whether rapid phase overwriting could destabilize the local phase field, preventing cluster stabilization and promoting local mixing.

To qualitatively support our segregation hypothesis, we use two complementary approaches: a simplified mean-field approximation and a swarmalator pair analysis. The mean-field approximation (Appendix A) isolates the basic segregation mechanism by examining a single swarmalator in a static phase environment, revealing a segregation tendency and suggesting a potential limit cycle. The swarmalator pair analysis (Appendix B) assesses phase-locking stability in a nonlinear model, demonstrating how segregation patterns emerge. This continuum-field approach complements our numerical simulations' discrete lattice model.

III. MEASURES FOR EVALUATION OF SIMULATIONS AT NONEQUILIBRIUM CONDITIONS

A. Mean square displacement

To examine swarmalator displacements under non-equilibrium conditions, we introduce a modified measure for the Mean Square Displacement (MSD). The system starts from randomized initial positions, and early movements arise from stochastic variations rather than an ordered transport mechanism. This randomness shapes how displacements develop over time. The mean squared displacement (MSD) quantifies the average squared distance a swarmalator travels from its initial position over time, averaged across all swarmalators and independent simulation restarts. It is defined as:

$$MSD(t) = \frac{1}{N n_{rep}} \sum_{n=1}^{n_{rep}} \sum_{i=1}^N \|\mathbf{r}_i^{(n)}(t) - \mathbf{r}_i^{(n)}(0)\|^2, \quad (8)$$

where N is the total number of swarmalators, n_{rep} is the number of independent simulation restarts, $\mathbf{r}_i^{(n)}(0)$ denotes the initial position of swarmalator i in the n -th restart, and $\mathbf{r}_i^{(n)}(t)$ is its position at time t in the same restart. For each swarmalator in each restart, we compute the squared Euclidean distance between the initial ($\mathbf{r}_i^{(n)}(0)$) and current ($\mathbf{r}_i^{(n)}(t)$) positions.

The result is then averaged over all N swarmalators and all n_{rep} restarts.

B. Statistical characterization of bimodal swarmalator system

This paper examines the emergent indirect interactions in a system consisting of two distinct swarmalator groups: type A and type B , each with a specific angular velocity. To statistically analyze these interactions, we employ pairwise correlation measures that quantify spatial affinity between type A and type B swarmalators, as well as the clustering tendency within each type. The motion of the swarmalators is constrained within a square arena $\Lambda = [0, L] \times [0, L]$, later modified by the presence of an additional barrier.

For a swarmalator indexed by i , the neighborhood \mathcal{U}_i is defined as the set of all other swarmalators j within a spatial correlation distance ℓ_{nn} :

$$\mathcal{U}_i \equiv \{j \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\} \mid j \neq i, \|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j\| < \ell_{nn}, \mathbf{r}_j \in \Lambda\}. \quad (9)$$

Technically, in an N even system, swarmalator types are distinguished by partitioning the index set $\{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ into even indices (j such that $j \bmod 2 = 0$, denoted as set $\mathcal{A} \equiv \{j \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\} \mid j \bmod 2 = 0\}$) and odd indices (j such that $j \bmod 2 = 1$, denoted as set $\mathcal{B} \equiv \{j \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\} \mid j \bmod 2 = 1\}$). For each swarmalator i , the counts of neighbors belonging to sets \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} are defined as:

$$g_i^A = \sum_{j=1}^N \mathbb{I}(j \in \mathcal{U}_i) \mathbb{I}(j \in \mathcal{A}), \quad g_i^B = \sum_{j=1}^N \mathbb{I}(j \in \mathcal{U}_i) \mathbb{I}(j \in \mathcal{B}), \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbb{I}(\cdot)$ is the indicator function, which assigns a value of one if the input meets a specified condition and a value of zero if it does not. At a distance ℓ_{nn} , an indicator function quantifies relationships between swarmalators based on their spatial arrangement. Summing its values over all swarmalators yields the correlation counts:

$$\begin{aligned} g^{AA} &= \sum_{i=1}^N g_i^A \mathbb{I}(i \in \mathcal{A}), & g^{AB} &= \sum_{i=1}^N g_i^B \mathbb{I}(i \in \mathcal{A}), \\ g^{BA} &= \sum_{i=1}^N g_i^A \mathbb{I}(i \in \mathcal{B}), & g^{BB} &= \sum_{i=1}^N g_i^B \mathbb{I}(i \in \mathcal{B}). \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

These counts characterize the spatial distribution and correlations of different swarmalator types, aiding in pattern analysis.

To quantify synchronization from the perspective of i , we modify the standard order parameter using the cosine of the phase difference $\phi_i - \phi_j$:

$$\begin{aligned} s_i^A &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^N \mathbb{I}(j \in \mathcal{U}_i) \mathbb{I}(j \in \mathcal{A}) [1 + \cos(\phi_i - \phi_j)], \\ s_i^B &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^N \mathbb{I}(j \in \mathcal{U}_i) \mathbb{I}(j \in \mathcal{B}) [1 + \cos(\phi_i - \phi_j)]. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

This formulation accounts for phase differences and utilizes the term $\frac{1}{2}[1 + \cos(\phi_i - \phi_j)]$, which is bounded between 0 and 1. A value of 1 indicates perfect synchronization, and a value of 0 indicates complete desynchronization.

To normalize these measures and account for differences in swarmalator counts (g_i^A, g_i^B), we define systemic synchronization as:

$$\begin{aligned} s^{AA} &= \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{s_i^A}{g_i^A} \mathbb{I}(i \in \mathcal{A}), & s^{AB} &= \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{s_i^B}{g_i^A} \mathbb{I}(i \in \mathcal{A}), \\ s^{BA} &= \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{s_i^A}{g_i^B} \mathbb{I}(i \in \mathcal{B}), & s^{BB} &= \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{s_i^B}{g_i^B} \mathbb{I}(i \in \mathcal{B}). \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

By summing the diagonal ($diag = AA, BB$) and off-diagonal ($mix = AB, BA$) components separately, we simplify the analysis of intra-group and inter-group interactions while preserving essential dynamical information. The diagonal terms describe interactions within the same group, while the off-diagonal terms capture interactions between different groups. The summing transformation decreases the number of independent measures and provides clearer insights into the statistical consequences of the interactions:

$$\begin{bmatrix} g^{diag} \\ g^{mix} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} g^{AA} \\ g^{BB} \\ g^{AB} \\ g^{BA} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (14)$$

with an analogous expression for s -measures. This compact representation makes the roles of each component clearer and reduces overall complexity.

C. Quantification of Barrier-Influenced Segregation

In previous considerations of finite systems with boundaries, a focus on the impact of these boundaries, particularly reflexive ones, on the swarmalator mixture behavior was lacking. To address this, we introduce G_{AB}^{bulk} , a measure that accounts for the system's geometry and boundary conditions. This measure effectively quantifies the spatial segregation between group types A and B , incorporating the effect of a horizontal internal barrier of length L_{bar} , which partitions the simulation arena into two equal-sized regions. The barrier (Fig. 2 B) extends across the left half of the square arena and is parallel to the x -axis.

We defined N_A^+ and N_B^+ as the number of swarmalators from group types A and B , respectively, positioned above the barrier (with zero size allowed). The "+" subscript signifies the 'above-barrier' region. We have:

$$N_A^+ = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} \mathbb{I}(y_i > L_{bar}), \quad N_B^+ = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{B}} \mathbb{I}(y_i > L_{bar}),$$

where y_i represents the vertical position of swarmalator i . Each group has at most $N/2$ swarmalators above the barrier: $N_A^+ \leq N/2$ and $N_B^+ \leq N/2$.

To quantify deviations from perfect spatial segregation, which we define as proximity to either of two ideal macrostates (macrostate 1 : $N_A^+ = N/2, N_B^+ = 0$ or macrostate 2 : $N_A^+ = 0, N_B^+ = N/2$), we introduce auxiliary coefficients q_A and q_B . These coefficients, defined

as $q_A = \frac{|N_A^+ - \frac{N}{2}| + N_B^+}{N}$ and $q_B = \frac{|N_B^+ - \frac{N}{2}| + N_A^+}{N}$, effectively measure the Manhattan distances to macrostates 1 and 2, respectively. The segregation measure G_{AB}^{bulk} can then be defined as

$$G_{AB}^{bulk} = 1 - 2 \min\{q_A, q_B\}, \quad (15)$$

ranging from 0 for complete mixing to 1 for perfect segregation. By employing the minimum function, $\min\{q_A, q_B\}$, the measure G_{AB}^{bulk} inherently embodies a logical "OR" condition. That is, G_{AB}^{bulk} is large when the system approaches either macrostate 1 (small q_A) or macrostate 2 (small q_B), thus capturing the dominant segregation outcome. Consistent with this definition, G_{AB}^{bulk} correctly predicts no segregation ($G_{AB}^{bulk} = 1 - 2\nu - |2\nu - 1| = 0$) when the number of swarmalators from each group above the barrier is equal, $N_A^+ = N_B^+ = \nu N$, where $0 < \nu \leq 1/2$. Conversely, G_{AB}^{bulk} is expected to be maximized, approaching perfect segregation ($G_{AB}^{bulk} = 1$), when N_A^+ and N_B^+ are maximally different, specifically when $N_A^+ = \nu N$ and $N_B^+ = (\frac{1}{2} - \nu)N$.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we present numerical results exploring emergent behaviors in a swarmalator system driven by non-equilibrium dynamics. Simulations were conducted in a spatially dense lattice environment, with parameters carefully constrained by physical validity and numerical stability (Table I). To probe distinct dynamical regimes, we systematically varied the key control parameters: the intrinsic angular velocity ω_A and the stigmergy-mediated coupling strength K_{np} . The angular velocity ω_A was specifically chosen to maintain resolvable orbital motion, while the coupling strength K_{np} covered the range from weak to strong phase synchronization effects. Careful attention was paid to spatial and interaction parameters: the lattice spacing ℓ_{lat} provided approximately 10 sampling points per orbital circumference, even for the most rapid rotations ($\omega_A \gtrsim 1$), thereby guaranteeing smooth trajectory integration. Additionally, swarmalator repulsion was precisely calibrated to prevent clustering below the lattice scale (thus $\ell_{pp} \gtrsim \ell_{lat}$ and $k_{pp} \gtrsim 1$), ensuring physically meaningful contact interactions. The statistical study of non-equilibrium states required simulation time horizons (t_H) long enough to encompass multiple rotation cycles. For instance, with $t_H = 10^6$ elementary time steps ($\Delta t = 0.002$ assumed), the number of complete rotation cycles ranged from approximately 30 for $\omega_A = 0.1$ to 500 for $\omega_A = 1.6$. The integration time step Δt satisfied dual stability criteria: $\omega_A \Delta t \ll 1$ to resolve phase evolution, and $v_{pr} \Delta t \ll \ell_{lat}$ to prevent spatial undersampling. Ultimately, statistical reliability was ensured through extensive ensemble averaging across repeated simulations (n_{rep}).

This study examines aspects of segregation, focusing on the influence of K_{pn} and ω_A . We restrict the analysis to the symmetric case $K_{np} = K_{pn} > 0$, ensuring balanced stigmergy-mediated information exchange among swarmalators and environment. The instantaneous mean values (averaged over n_{rep} runs) are used to characterize spatial coordination and synchronization.

Symbol	Value	Description
n_{rep}	{40, 600}	number of random reinitializations
N	200	total number of active swarmalators
t_H	$\sim 10^4 - 10^6$	time horizons (multiples of Δt)
M	100	number of lattice nodes along one dimension
L	10	side length of the square arena
L_{bar}	$\leq (3/4)L$	barrier length
ℓ_{lat}	$L/M = 0.1$	lattice spacing between adjacent nodes
ℓ_{pp}	$3\ell_{lat} = 0.3$	spacing parameter of swarmalator repulsion
v_{pr}	0.3	velocity of self-propelled swarmalators
Δt	0.002	integration time step
k_{pp}	2.0	swarmalator-swarmalator repulsion coefficient
ω_A	(0, 1.6]	A-type swarmalator angular velocity
σ_T	10^{-2}	standard deviation of the torque distribution
$\sigma_T\sqrt{\Delta t}$	4.47×10^{-4}	increment in torque for Wiener process
ℓ_{nn}	$2\ell_{pp}$	spatial correlation distance (exceptions: Appendix C)
K_{np}	0, 0.01, ..., 0.4	variants of the swarmalator-to-node coupling

TABLE I: Simulation parameters for swarmalator dynamics: lattice details, computational aspects, and interaction strengths.

A. Analyzing Pair Correlation Measures to Quantify Segregation

To quantify spatial coordination statistically, we computed the mean value $\langle g^{diag} \rangle(t)$ for the diagonal pair and the mean value $\langle g^{mix} \rangle(t)$ for the mixed pair, using measures from independent realizations of simulations starting from random initial configurations. To gain insights into non-equilibrium phenomena, we employed time horizons (t_H) to differentiate between rapid and slow relaxation phases, allowing us to highlight the associated segregation phenomena at different timescales. To gain insights into the emergent structures and the influence of various parameters, the *Supplemental Material* provides simulation snapshots depicting how K_{np} , ω_A , and t_H shape the swarm morphology, including cases with and without barrier-influenced boundary conditions.

Based on this established framework, we focused on identifying the onset of relevant stigmergy-mediated interactions in our system through statistical evaluation. We began by examining the effect of zero and vanishingly small K_{np} values for $\omega_A = 0.2$ on the time evolution of $g^{diag}(t)$ and $g^{mix}(t)$, as shown in Fig. 3. In the absence of stigmergy ($K_{np} = 0$), local segregation is reflected in the low mean values of $\langle g^{diag} \rangle(t)$ and $\langle g^{mix} \rangle(t)$. The systematic differences in these mean values are attributed to more favorable movement conditions that arise when swarmalators of the same type follow each other in tandem. A marginal increase in K_{np} (e.g., reaching 0.01) leads to the immediate emergence of stigmergy-mediated influences, although a precise activation threshold has not been numerically determined. Moreover, for values of K_{np} below 0.01, the onset of stigmergy-mediated effects is not readily observable—a limitation influenced by both the resolution of the analysis for a given t_H and the number of statistical events considered. Notwithstanding these challenges, the simulation data suggest that stigmergy-mediated effects emerge continuously from a zero level rather than at a distinct activation point. Thus, $K_{np} = 0$ marks the transition to the segregation regime at a given resolution, and detecting any effects at these low inter-

FIG. 3: Nonequilibrium g -measures scatterplots (Eq. 11) for local segregation analysis at $\omega_A = 0.2$. Simulations explore stigmergy-mediated interaction effects at $K_{np} \in \{0, 0.01\}$, ($t_H = 2 \times 10^6$). Plots show K_{np} -dependent increase in $\langle g^{diag} \rangle - \langle g^{mix} \rangle$, with persistent difference at $K_{np} = 0$ (drag-induced). Representative, selected g^{diag} trajectories and $n_{rep} = 40$ run averages (dashed lines) are depicted.

action levels—where changes are expected to be minimal or absent—necessitated a large observation horizon ($t_H = 2 \times 10^6$).

A significantly smaller horizon ($t_H = 4 \times 10^5$) was sufficient to capture the system's behavior in Fig. 4 for stronger stigmergy-mediated interactions. We analyzed the system's response across various interaction strengths, including lower values ($K_{pn} = 0.1, 0.2$) and a stronger coupling ($K_{pn} = 0.4$), as well as intermediate $\omega_A = 0.2$; this ω_A yields circular trajectories with $r_{p,i} = v_{pr}/\omega_A \simeq 1.5$ (see Eq. 7). For $\ell_{nn} = 0.6$ (where $\ell_{nn} = 2\ell_{pp}$), segregation g -measures were evaluated across the studied cases, with this value being comparable to r_p and much smaller than L . Temporal exploration revealed an increase in $\langle g^{diag} \rangle(t)$, signifying enhanced local segregation, while $\langle g^{mix} \rangle(t)$ remained consistently lower. The trends of increasing $\langle g^{diag} \rangle$ and decreasing $\langle g^{mix} \rangle$ are qualitatively the same across all panels (A, C, and E). At a high value of $K_{np} = 0.4$, the increase in $\langle g^{diag} \rangle$ (and the corresponding decrease in $\langle g^{mix} \rangle$) is quite rapid, with saturation reached more quickly. In some system realizations (individual runs), irregular oscillations, also observed in the MSD , can be attributed to perturbed orbital motion. These oscillations in $MSD(t)$ (as further elaborated below) are a key indicator of the crossover in transport behavior, influenced by system boundaries.

Complementing this statistical analysis, the system's dynamics were also characterized using $MSD(t)$, as defined by Eq. (8). Initially, as expected for a system undergoing diffusion, $MSD(t)$ exhibited a linear growth with time, as presented in Fig. 4 (panels B, D, F). The main contribution to this initial behavior arises from irregularities, such as the initial random phase of swarmalators, environmental influences, and inter-swarmalator collisions.

Subsequently, $MSD(t)$ reveals a non-equilibrium transition from predominantly stochastic motion to synchronized, oscillatory relaxation. This transition is marked by the emergence of macroscopic oscillations in $MSD(t)$, visible both before and significantly beyond the first peak ($\sim 0.5 \times 10^5$). The finer oscillations correspond to a lower timescale period

FIG. 4: Comparing nonequilibrium scatterplots of g -measures (Eqs. 11, 14) and Mean Squared Displacement $MSD(t)$ (Eq. 8) for varying K_{np} (0.1, 0.2, 0.4; $\omega_A = 0.2$). Averages (dashed, $n_{rep} = 40$) and single run paths (continuous black) shown. The plots highlight K_{np} 's influence on system dynamics and spatial coordination, particularly demonstrating the transition from a diffusive regime to a boundary-induced oscillatory regime with a quasi-ballistic component in the long-time $MSD(t)$ behavior.

FIG. 5: Scatterplot comparison of ω_A dependencies on diagonal and non-diagonal g -measures, as defined in Eq. (11). Data from nonequilibrium simulations at $K_{np} = 0.1, 0.2, 0.4$, averaged over $n_{rep} = 40$ restarts. Dashed lines show means for $t_H = 10^5$ and 2×10^5 steps.

of approximately $(2\pi/(\omega_A \Delta t) \approx 0.16 \times 10^5)$ time steps. Crucially, longer-period oscillations with a duration of $\sim 10^5$ steps are also observed. These longer-period oscillations are directly attributable to recurrent reflections at the system boundaries. This effect leads

FIG. 6: The figure shows the difference between diagonal (s^{diag} , upper branches) and non-diagonal (s^{mix} , lower branches) s -measures, calculated using Eq. (13) for interaction strengths $K_{np} = 0.1$ (panel A) and 0.4 (panel B). This demonstrates how synchronization of swarmalators behave as a function of ω_A at a time horizon of $t_H = 2 \times 10^5$ steps. More abrupt changes were observed for the higher interaction strength ($K_{np} = 0.4$). The instantaneous mean values were computed using $n_{rep} = 40$ repetitions.

to swarmalators repeatedly returning to and moving away from their initial coordinates, inducing a quasi-ballistic component in the long-time dynamics. This observed behavior in $MSD(t)$ therefore exemplifies a crossover from a purely diffusive regime to one where boundary-induced, quasi-ballistic traversals dominate, providing deeper insights into the interplay between inherent random motion and spatial confinement.

To understand broader quantitative aspects of segregation, we now examine the dependence of the g -measures on the parameter ω_A . Fig. 5 presents the dependence of both g^{diag} and g^{mix} on ω_A for fixed K_{np} , considering time horizons of $t_H = 10^5$ and 2×10^5 steps. The mean values of g^{diag} exhibit peaks around $\omega_A \approx 0.2$ – 0.4 . The trends in $\langle g^{mix} \rangle(\omega_A, t_H)$ essentially mirror those of $\langle g^{diag} \rangle(\omega_A, t_H)$.

As demonstrated in Fig. 5, for low values of ω_A (say $\omega_A < 0.1$), segregation remains weak and largely independent of K_{np} . This can be attributed to straighter trajectories, more frequent boundary reflections and inter-particle collisions. As ω_A increases, segregation strengthens, reaching an optimum at intermediate values. Beyond this optimum, further increases in ω_A lead to a decrease in segregation as the orbital radius r_p becomes too small to support large-scale organization.

With strong coupling strength ($K_{np} = 0.4$), distinct clustering of type A and type B swarmalators into homogeneous groups is observed. The emergence of complex morphologies, evidenced by a double peak in the $\langle g^{diag} \rangle$ versus ω_A plot, is critically sensitive to the correlation distance ℓ_{nn} employed in the g - and s -measure calculations (see Fig. 11 in Appendix C).

This study identifies a strong interdependence between phase synchronization in type A/B swarmalators and their spatial segregation. Quantitative analysis reveals that synchronization statistics—derived from the s -measures (Eq. 13; Fig. 6)—exhibit statistical

congruence with spatial segregation metrics calculated using g -measures. This alignment suggests a bidirectional coupling between phase correlations and positional configurations, demonstrating that phase synchronization drives emergent spatial self-organization.

To visually comprehend the emergent swarm behavior and complement our statistical analyses, we refer to Fig. 7. This figure displays simulation snapshots at time points $t_H \in \{3 \times 10^4, 3 \times 10^5, 3 \times 10^6\}$, illustrating specific cluster formation at parameters $\omega_A = 0.2$ and $K_{np} = 0.1$, starting from a random initial state in both position and environmental phases.

The illustrative snapshots from panels C and D highlight mobility-induced segregation, consistent with [44, 45]. While this phenomenon is characteristic of self-propelled particle systems, in our model segregation specifically arises from stigmergy-mediated feedback. Swarmalators at the front of moving clusters experience greater environmental phase asynchrony compared to those in the interior. This mismatch decelerates the front and promotes accumulation, leading to distinct dense and sparse regions.

Of particular interest is the emergence of higher-density domains of either type A or B . As seen in Fig. 7 (panels D–F), the swarmalator rings break into dense areas along circular orbits. In dense regions, repulsive interactions promote pseudo-crystalline (hexagonal) ordering [24] with higher mobility, while sparse areas are occupied by slower, disorganized, gas-like swarmalators.

Our work focuses on a specific type of segregation—spatial separation into types A and B —driven by phase-dependent motion (see Eq. 5 and Fig. 7 E,F). For certain values of ω_A (such as 0.1 or 0.2), complex interplay between cluster formation and radial segregation occurs, often resulting in composite structures with a dense core of one type surrounded by a wetting peripheral layer of the other type.

The expected changes in the dynamics and shape of the wetting layer become particularly evident under the influence of an internal barrier, as illustrated in Fig. 8.

B. Barrier-Influenced Segregation Results

Building upon the discussion of local segregation through g -measures of pairwise correlations, we now turn to quantifying bulk segregation at the systemic level. Bulk segregation can be characterized by a large-scale separation of components into the predefined compartments of the system, which can be characterized by the measure G_{AB}^{bulk} proposed in Eq. (15).

The previous part of the section demonstrated the conditions under which segregation occurs via stigmergy, while this section investigates the mechanisms by which boundary barriers control and modulate this segregation. For the design of our boundary barriers, we drew inspiration from the analogy with semipermeable interfaces, where partial flow of particles is crucial for segregation. The expected changes in the dynamics and shape of the wetting layer are of particular importance, as illustrated in, for example, Fig. 8.

This modulation is achieved by implementing a horizontal barrier aligned along the x -axis that symmetrically bisects the simulation arena along the y -axis into upper and lower compartments (see Fig. 2). The rationale behind this approach is that such barriers may partially disrupt the integrity of the wetting layer, thereby inducing an alternative flow pattern generated by the barrier’s curvature (modulated by ω_A and the corners). This flow

FIG. 7: Simulated non-equilibrium environmental phase patterns (left A, C, E) with corresponding positions and trajectories (right B, D, F) of swarmalators for $K_{np} = 0.1$, $\omega_A = 0.2$. Right panels show type A (red \triangle) and type B (blue \rightarrow) swarmalators with past positions. Circular trajectories and segmented clusters are seen in panels C and D. Panels C-F reveal central type A condensation and peripheral type B wetting.

FIG. 8: Changes in the segregation of types A and B , particularly along the y axis in the bulk, are revealed in snapshots of a system with a central boundary barrier ($L_{bar} = L/2$). Comparing interaction strengths $K_{np} = 0.1$ and 0.4 ($\omega_A = 0.2$ fixed) highlights qualitative differences: at $K_{np} = 0.4$, clusters demonstrate sharper interfaces, increased structural stability, and reduced translational mobility, exhibiting primarily diffusive behavior.

directs particles into the upper or lower sections and imposes an additional constraint on the swarmalators' natural circular motion, facilitating separation prior to the establishment of complete bulk segregation. The configuration of the barrier, with a length of $L_{bar} = L/2$, along with the corresponding swarmalator distribution, is depicted in Fig. 8.

With the aim of determining the influence of barrier length L_{bar} on bulk segregation statistics within specific parametric regimes ($K_{np} = 0.1, 0.4$; $\omega_A = 0.2$), we systematically varied barrier lengths ($L_{bar} = 0, L/4, L/2, 3L/4$) in a horizontal configuration and evaluated the resulting statistical properties of the swarmalator system. The extent of bulk segregation was quantitatively assessed using the G_{AB}^{bulk} metric (Eq. 15) in steady-state configurations at the final simulation time, $t_H = 2 \times 10^6$. To obtain statistically robust and stable histograms of G_{AB}^{bulk} , we employed an extensive random initialization procedure, using numerous initial-

FIG. 9: Histograms of the non-equilibrium statistics for G_{AB}^{bulk} , illustrating the influence of the barrier's linear dimension L_{bar} on the segregation process. The results are presented for $\omega_A = 0.2$, two interaction cases, and $t_H = 2 \times 10^6$.

izations ($n_{rep} = 600$) for randomly generated initial mixtures of A and B -type swarms.

Initiated from random initial conditions, the self-organization of the swarms system statistically manifests as a probability distribution profile of G_{AB}^{bulk} (Fig. 9). Even in the benchmark case of $L_{bar} = 0$, the broad distribution of G_{AB}^{bulk} reveals that segregation along the y -axis can still occur, with the system exhibiting larger fluctuations near the $G_{AB}^{bulk} = 1$ limit for $K_{np} = 0.1$ and a more restrictive effect at higher $K_{np} = 0.4$. This baseline scenario, where segregation emerges despite the absence of barriers, underscores the inherent drive towards self-organization within the system. Given that stigmergy-mediated action, while nonlocal, has a limited effective range, the influence of boundary barriers on segregation becomes

increasingly pronounced as L_{bar} increases. At $L_{bar} = L/4$, the likelihood of segregation rises, while a significant shift in the G_{AB}^{bulk} distribution is observed at $L_{bar} = L/2$. At this length, a trimodal distribution emerges, with peaks in G_{AB}^{bulk} near 0, 0.5, and 1, suggesting that barriers reshape swarm dynamics by selectively filtering and reinforcing configurations. Instead of merely impeding movement, barriers appear to establish preferred states, temporarily trapping the system and leading to probability accumulation at specific G_{AB}^{bulk} values, which form the observed peaks.

For $L_{bar} = 3L/4$, the distribution exhibits a pronounced peak at $G_{AB}^{bulk} \sim 1$, along with a local minimum at $G_{AB}^{bulk} = 0.9$, indicating that certain subsets of initial configurations are less favored by the barriers. Generally, with increasing stigmergic strength (typically observed for $K_{np} = 0.4$), the system becomes more rigid, resulting in reduced mobility and a greater tendency to settle into specific configurations. This finding highlights the complex and nonlinear dependence of emergent collective dynamics on barrier geometry. The emergence of dense traveling ring-shaped clusters with sharp boundaries and limited mobility (see Fig. 8) exemplifies strong bulk segregation at $K_{np} = 0.4$. Our model does not explicitly include attachment forces; however, the observed configurations indicate that pinning emerges spontaneously due to restricted mobility and geometric confinement. This emergent phenomenon is consistent with the general principle of synchronization disruption by localized obstacles, akin to barriers, as seen in studies like [37] where pinning sites play a similar role.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we investigate the fundamental mechanisms governing pattern formation in heterogeneous swarmalator systems composed of types A and B with different senses of rotation but the same orbital size. A key innovation of our approach is the incorporation of indirect, nonlocal interactions inspired by the concept of stigmergy. This feature distinguishes it from existing approaches.

The simulations demonstrate that the separation of swarmalators into distinct clusters of type A and type B is primarily driven by stigmergy—their indirect communication through environmental phase changes. While their individual phase rotation influences their curved paths, it is this stigmergy-mediated interaction that orchestrates the segregation.

Along their established trajectories, we observe that certain swarmalators exhibit partially frozen phases with specific configurations. These phases appear to play a crucial role in maintaining rotational coherence within the clusters. This phenomenon introduces a novel mechanism contributing to segregation distinct from mobility-induced effects [44, 45]. Specifically, the presence of these partially frozen phases may stabilize the synchronized rotational states within homogeneous clusters, thereby facilitating their separation.

For a detailed summary of the identified phenomena, their causal relationships, and their place in current research, refer to Table II.

While our study focuses on a theoretical model of swarmalators, the observed segregation and coherence driven by stigmergy and partially frozen phases offer intriguing parallels with the dynamic organization of living systems. For instance, bacterial biofilms, particularly

those formed by *Vibrio cholerae* [51], exhibit non-equilibrium structural changes mediated by stigmergy-driven processes involving the extracellular matrix. Notably, *Vibrio cholerae* is crescent-shaped, a structural feature that imparts a chirality reminiscent of the imposed rotational chirality in our swarmalators and their clusters. The insights gained from our tractable swarmalator model, regarding the environmental feedback in driving self-organization, may provide a valuable framework for future investigations into the analogous processes observed in living systems.

By utilizing the G_{AB}^{bulk} metric, we have established that barriers reorganize local order, effectively channeling it to form global patterns. This significant finding challenges the traditional perspective of barriers as merely simple obstacles, hinting at a novel and potentially powerful role in swarm systems.

TABLE II: Detailed summary of distinct emergent phenomena in stigmergy-coupled chiral swarmalators, describing the specific phase-field mediated mechanisms and their correspondence or contrast to phenomena documented in the contemporary literature.

Phenomenon	Specific mechanism	Relation to literature
Stigmergic segregation	Phase-dependent motion along stigmergic trajectories separates opposite-chirality swarmalators through environmental feedback.	Extends chirality-driven segregation in [35]; reveals role of phase field memory in domain stabilization.
Vortex pattern formation	Identical-chirality swarmalators form stable vortices via phase alignment, while mixed chirality creates turbulent interfaces.	Contrasts vortex states in [52]; stabilization requires stigmergic field coupling.
Radial core-shell clustering	Phase gradient feedback induces concentric domains during relaxation, with inner clusters surrounded by wetting layers.	Refines radial layering in [24]; driven by nonequilibrium relaxation dynamics.
Barrier-induced pinning	Geometric confinement at barriers immobilizes clusters through restricted mobility and stigmergy-mediated phase field reshaping.	Parallels obstacle-induced pinning in [37]; here emerging spontaneously from environmental feedback.
Mobility-induced phase separation	Phase mismatch at cluster interfaces jamming and density variation during collective motion.	Complements density asynchrony in [38]; segregation emerges without direct attraction.

Inspired by biological swarms, our barrier-influenced framework offers a pathway to autonomous robotics via stigmergy-mediated environmental encoding (phase cues and motion

vectors) for structural control without direct communication [55]. This aligns with robotic applications by Eguchi et al. [56]. Future work should prioritize experimental validation on stigmergy-enabled robotic platforms [57, 58] to harness retrievable cues and motion vectors, ultimately enabling scalable real-world applications with minimalist prototypes and enhancing sophisticated swarm system design and control.

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Appendix A: Single swarmalator in a double vortex field

This appendix details a simplified mean-field analysis employed to investigate segregation phenomena in swarmalator systems. Utilizing a static phase field approximation, effectively representing a time-invariant environment, this approach provides a tractable framework for the controlled examination of specific segregation tendencies. It is important to note that this analytical method differs fundamentally from comprehensive self-organizing simulations, where the environmental phase field emerges dynamically from the system’s internal interactions.

The dynamics of a single swarmalator of type A , derived from Eq.(5), is considered next:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d\phi_A}{dt} &= \omega_A + K_{np} \sin(\Phi(x_A, y_A) - \phi_A), \\ \frac{dx_A}{dt} &= v_{pr} \cos(\phi_A), \\ \frac{dy_A}{dt} &= v_{pr} \sin(\phi_A).\end{aligned}\tag{A1}$$

Here, the phase $\phi_A(t)$ determines the swarmalator’s motion, while $x_A(t)$ and $y_A(t)$ denote its Cartesian coordinates, which are dynamically coupled to ϕ_A . To induce A/B segregation (sorting) through opposing rotational motions, we define a static phase field environment:

$$\Phi(x, y) = \pi \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{sgn}(x) \right) + \operatorname{atan2}(y, x - \operatorname{sgn}(x)r_p) .\tag{A2}$$

This configuration creates two distinct environments: (i) left vortex (environment congruent with A that drives counter-clockwise rotation (for $x < 0$); (ii) right vortex (environment B)

FIG. 10: Single swarmalator trajectories in a chosen static double-vortex field $\Phi(x, y)$. (A) Trajectory trials under the effect of $\Phi(x, y)$, showing velocity vectors of the swarmalator and two Φ vortices centered at $(\pm r_p, 0)$ that support opposing rotational directions. Trials with swarmalators of type *A* converge to the limit cycles in the congruent environment (label: env *A*) of the counter-clockwise rotation in the right vortex $(r_p, 0)$. The counter-clockwise domain with the left vortex (blue arrows; label: env *B*) is unstable for *A* type swarmalators. Interface region $x = 0$ of $\Phi(x, y)$ exhibits prolonged oscillatory transient dynamics before converging to limit cycle. (B) The temporal evolutions of trajectories converging to a limit cycle corresponding to the nine initial conditions parameterized as: $x_A|_{t=0} = 5(i_1 - 1)$, $y_A|_{t=0} = 5(i_2 - 1)$, $\phi_A|_{t=0} = (\pi/2)i_3$, where i_1, i_2, i_3 are integer indices from $\{0, 1, 2\}$; nine visible gray empty squares denote (x, y) projections of these initial conditions.

that drives clockwise rotation (for $x > 0$). The term $x - \text{sgn}(x)r_p$ shifts the vortex centers by r_p along the x -axis, ensuring a spatial interface at $x = 0$.

For simulations visualized in Fig. 10, we used parameters $v_{pr} = 0.3$, $\omega_A = 0.1$, $r_p = 3.0$, and $K_{np} = 0.3$. Initial conditions were drawn from a hypercube, as detailed in the caption. The swarmalator consistently converges to a limit cycle attractor, regardless of initial conditions.

Appendix B: Counter-rotating Swarmalator Pair: Phase-locking and Spatial Segregation

This appendix analyzes the dynamics of two swarmalators coupled via environmental phase fields, focusing on phase-locking and emergent spatial segregation. The minimal continuous model elucidates how phase field geometry governs pattern formation, revealing frequency mismatch effects, synchronization transitions, and motility-phase coupling. We identify phase-locked states in three asymptotic spatial configurations, explaining segregation observed in simulations. Notably, this model focuses exclusively on environmental phase

field coupling, deliberately excluding mutual contact interactions between swarmalators.

1. Model Formulation

The dynamics for swarmalators $\nu \in \{A, B\}$ are governed by:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{r}_\nu}{dt} = v_{pr} \begin{pmatrix} \cos \phi_\nu \\ \sin \phi_\nu \end{pmatrix}, \quad (\text{B1})$$

$$\frac{d\phi_\nu}{dt} = (\delta_{\nu,A} - \delta_{\nu,B})\omega_A + K_{np} \sum_{\sigma=\pm} \sin(\Phi_\sigma - \phi_\nu) I(\sigma x_\nu), \quad (\text{B2})$$

$$\frac{d\Phi_\sigma}{dt} = K_{np} \sum_{\nu \in \{A,B\}} \sin(\phi_\nu - \Phi_\sigma) I(\sigma x_\nu), \quad (\text{B3})$$

where the spatial weight $I(x) = \frac{1}{2}[1 + \tanh(\beta x)]$, with $\beta > 0$, partitions the x -axis. This continuous function $I(x)$ models the influence of stigmergy, serving as a continuous analogue to the discrete lattice nodes previously used to represent environmental phase fields. In effect, it replaces two distinct lattice nodes by spreading their influence continuously across the half-planes. For $x \gg 0$, $I(x) \rightarrow 1$; for $x \ll 0$, $I(x) \rightarrow 0$, ensuring swarmalator ν couples primarily to Φ_+ when $x_\nu \gg 0$ and to Φ_- when $x_\nu \ll 0$. The parameter β controls the interface steepness, approximating binary coupling for large β . This model captures stigmergic feedback through instantaneous environmental interactions. We seek phase-locked states ($\dot{\phi}_\nu = 0$, $\dot{\Phi}_\sigma = 0$) with constant velocities $\mathbf{V}_\nu^* = (V_{x,\nu}^*, V_{y,\nu}^*)^\top$.

2. Phase-locked States and Segregation Mechanisms

We analyze three asymptotic regimes to characterize phase-locking and segregation.

a. Co-rotating Pair in the Right Half-space

When $x_A^*, x_B^* \rightarrow +\infty$, $I(x_\nu^*) \rightarrow 1$, so both swarmalators couple exclusively to Φ_+ . The phase dynamics reduce to:

$$\dot{\phi}_A = \omega_A + K_{np} \sin(\Phi_+ - \phi_A), \quad \dot{\phi}_B = -\omega_A + K_{np} \sin(\Phi_+ - \phi_B),$$

$$\dot{\Phi}_+ = K_{np} [\sin(\phi_A - \Phi_+) + \sin(\phi_B - \Phi_+)].$$

Phase-locking requires:

$$\omega_A + K_{np} \sin(\Phi_+^* - \phi_A^*) = 0, \quad -\omega_A + K_{np} \sin(\Phi_+^* - \phi_B^*) = 0,$$

$$\sin(\phi_A^* - \Phi_+^*) + \sin(\phi_B^* - \Phi_+^*) = 0.$$

Defining $\theta_A^* = \Phi_+^* - \phi_A^*$, $\theta_B^* = \Phi_+^* - \phi_B^*$, we obtain $\sin(\theta_A^*) = -\omega_A/K_{np}$, $\sin(\theta_B^*) = \omega_A/K_{np}$, and $\sin(\theta_A^*) + \sin(\theta_B^*) = 0$, satisfied when $\theta_A^* = -\theta_B^* = -\arcsin(\omega_A/K_{np})$, requiring $\omega_A \leq K_{np}$. The steady-state velocities are:

$$V_{x,\nu}^* = v_{pr} \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{\omega_A}{K_{np}}\right)^2}, \quad V_{y,A}^* = v_{pr} \frac{\omega_A}{K_{np}}, \quad V_{y,B}^* = -v_{pr} \frac{\omega_A}{K_{np}}.$$

The relative vertical speed, $\Delta V_y^* = V_{y,A}^* - V_{y,B}^* = 2v_{pr}\omega_A/K_{np}$, drives vertical segregation. Stability analysis via linearization yields the characteristic equation:

$$\lambda^3 + 2K_{np} \cos \theta_K^* \lambda^2 + (K_{np}^2 \cos^2 \theta_K^* + \beta^2 v_{pr}^2) \lambda + \beta^2 v_{pr}^2 K_{np} \cos \theta_K^* = 0,$$

where $\theta_K^* = \arcsin(\omega_A/K_{np})$. For $\omega_A < K_{np}$, all coefficients are positive, ensuring local stability. This regime supports synchronized motion with spatial segregation along the y -axis.

b. Pair Distributed over Opposite Half-spaces

For $x_A^* \rightarrow +\infty$, $x_B^* \rightarrow -\infty$, $I(x_A^*) \rightarrow 1$, $I(-x_B^*) \rightarrow 1$, so swarmalator A couples to Φ_+ and B to Φ_- . The dynamics are:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\phi}_A &= \omega_A + K_{np} \sin(\Phi_+ - \phi_A), & \dot{\phi}_B &= -\omega_A + K_{np} \sin(\Phi_- - \phi_B), \\ \dot{\Phi}_+ &= K_{np} \sin(\phi_A - \Phi_+), & \dot{\Phi}_- &= K_{np} \sin(\phi_B - \Phi_-). \end{aligned}$$

Fixed points satisfy:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \omega_A + K_{np} \sin(\Phi_+^* - \phi_A^*) \\ -\omega_A + K_{np} \sin(\Phi_-^* - \phi_B^*) \\ \sin(\phi_A^* - \Phi_+^*) \\ \sin(\phi_B^* - \Phi_-^*) \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{0}.$$

The field equations imply $\Phi_+^* = \phi_A^* + n\pi$, $\Phi_-^* = \phi_B^* + m\pi$, $n, m \in \mathbb{Z}$. Substituting yields $\omega_A = 0$, which contradicts $\omega_A > 0$. Thus, no phase-locked states exist. Defining $\theta_+ = \Phi_+ - \phi_A$, $\theta_- = \Phi_- - \phi_B$, we get:

$$\dot{\theta}_+ = -2K_{np} \sin(\theta_+) - \omega_A, \quad \dot{\theta}_- = -K_{np} \sin(\theta_-) + \omega_A.$$

No equilibria exist for $\omega_A > K_{np}$, leading to oscillatory phases. The velocities $\dot{\mathbf{r}}_\nu = v_{pr}(\cos \phi_\nu, \sin \phi_\nu)^\top$ become time-dependent, preventing straight-line motion. The fields Φ_+ and Φ_- evolve independently, eliminating stigmergic feedback and reinforcing spatial segregation.

c. Interfacial Dynamics

Near the interface ($x_\nu^* \approx 0$), $I(x_\nu^*) \approx 1/2$, so each swarmalator couples equally to Φ_+ and Φ_- . The phase dynamics are:

$$\dot{\phi}_\nu = (\delta_{\nu,A} - \delta_{\nu,B})\omega_A + \frac{K_{np}}{2} [\sin(\Phi_+ - \phi_\nu) + \sin(\Phi_- - \phi_\nu)].$$

Phase-locking requires $\omega_A < K_{np}/2$. However, the gradient $\frac{dI}{dx}|_{x=0} = \beta/4$ introduces sensitivity to perturbations δx_ν . Linearization shows instability when $\beta > K_{np}^2/(\omega_A v_{pr})$, with a divergence timescale of $(\beta v_{pr})^{-1}$. This instability drives swarms to opposite sides of the interface, where distinct phase environments suppress synchronization, facilitating long-term spatial segregation.

Appendix C: Spatial Correlation Distance as a Determinant of Morphology

This appendix aims to elucidate the origins of the double peak exhibited in the ω_A dependence of g^{diag} , as depicted in Fig. 5 E, for systems with $K_{np} = 0.4$. Our investigation centers on the commonly employed parameter choice $\ell_{nn} = 2\ell_{pp}$. To gain insight, we sought to establish a connection between ℓ_{nn} and the resulting statistical properties. Consequently, we proceeded to analyze the system's sensitivity to changes in ℓ_{nn} .

The results of calculations performed for ℓ_{nn} ranging from 1 to 5 times ℓ_{pp} are presented in Fig. 11. This figure demonstrates that the structure of the double peak of g^{diag} is influenced by the choice of ℓ_{nn} . The peak profile transitions from two asymmetric peaks to a single peak as ℓ_{nn} values approach $5\ell_{pp}$. This observation implies that a coarser selection of ℓ_{nn} reveals a typical mean size of cluster's outer contour; however, by looking at the sequence of $g^{diag}(\omega_A)$ dependencies obtained with smaller ℓ_{nn} , we may discern details that offer a morphological interpretation. The interpretation is consistent with the statistical effect of ring-shaped clusters, as depicted in Fig. 8 B,D (the presence of a barrier in the image is not relevant in this specific context).

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- [1] M. te Vrugt and R. Wittkowski, Metareview: a survey of active matter reviews, *Eur. Phys. J. E* **48**, 12 (2025). doi:10.1140/epje/s10189-024-00466-z
 - [2] T. Vicsek, A. Czirók, E. Ben-Jacob, I. Cohen, and O. Shochet, Novel type of phase transition in a system of self-driven particles, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **75**, 1226 (1995). doi:10.1103/PhysRevLett.75.1226
 - [3] A. M. Reynolds, G. E. McIvor, A. Thornton, P. Yang, and N. T. Ouellette, Stochastic modelling of bird flocks: accounting for the cohesiveness of collective motion, *J. R. Soc. Interface* **19**, 20210745 (2022). doi:10.1098/rsif.2021.0745
 - [4] M. Ballerini, N. Cabibbo, R. Candelier, A. Cavagna, E. Cisbani, E. Giardina, V. Lecomte, A. Orlandi, G. Parisi, A. Procaccini, M. Viale, and V. Zdravkovic, Interaction ruling animal collective behavior depends on topological rather than metric distance: Evidence from a field study, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **105**, 1232 (2008). doi:10.1073/pnas.0711437105
 - [5] C. W. Reynolds, Flocks, herds and schools: A distributed behavioral model, *Comput. Graph.* **21**, 25 (1987). doi:10.1145/37402.37406
 - [6] D. J. T. Sumpter, The principles of collective animal behavior, *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. B* **361**, 5 (2006). doi:10.1098/rstb.2005.1733
 - [7] P. R. Secor, L. A. Michaels, D. C. Bublitz, L. K. Jennings, and P. K. Singh, The Depletion

FIG. 11: Variations in ℓ_{nn} demonstrate the influence on double- and single-peak $\langle g^{diag} \rangle(\omega_A)$, thereby validating our interpretation. The several selected ℓ_{nn} values dynamic ring-shaped cluster formation. We emphasize $\ell_{nn} = 2\ell_{pp}$, which is the most frequently used value, and the largest $\ell_{nn} = 5\ell_{pp}$, which produces a single peak.

Mechanism Actuates Bacterial Aggregation by Exopolysaccharides and Determines Species Distribution & Composition in Bacterial Aggregates, *Front. Cell. Infect. Microbiol.* **12**, 869736 (2022). doi:10.3389/fcimb.2022.869736

- [8] D. Saintillan, Active suspensions, *Annu. Rev. Fluid Mech.* **50**, 563 (2018). doi: 10.1146/annurev-fluid-122316-045305
- [9] J. P. Steimel, J. L. Aragonés, H. Hu, N. Qureshi, and A. Alexander-Katz, Emergent ultra-long-range interactions between active particles in hybrid active-inactive systems, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **113**, 4652 (2016). doi:10.1073/pnas.1520481113
- [10] F. Ginot, I. Theurkauff, F. Detcheverry, C. Ybert, and C. Cottin-Bizonne, Aggregation-fragmentation and individual dynamics of active clusters, *Nat. Commun.* **9**, 696 (2018). doi: 10.1038/s41467-017-02625-7
- [11] G. Gardi, S. Ceron, W. Wang, K. Petersen, and M. Sitti, Microrobot collectives with re-

- configurable morphologies, behaviors, and functions, *Nat. Commun.* **13**, 2239 (2022). doi:10.1038/s41467-022-29882-5
- [12] N. Mahkam, A. Aghakhani, D. Sheehan, G. Gardi, R. Katzschmann, and M. Sitti, Acoustic Streaming-Induced Multimodal Locomotion of Bubble-Based Microrobots, *Adv. Sci.* **10**, 2304233 (2023). doi:10.1002/advs.202304233
- [13] A. Escobar, R. Reyes-Aguilar, C. G. Vidales-Hernández, J. L. Carrillo-Estrada, and F. Donado, Effect of particle concentration on the persistence of motion in active matter systems, *Physica A* **659**, 130344 (2025). doi:10.1016/j.physa.2024.130344
- [14] A. Ziepkke, I. Maryshev, I. S. Aranson, and E. Frey, Multi-scale organization in communicating active matter *Nat. Commun.* **13**, 6727 (2022). doi:10.1038/s41467-022-34484-2
- [15] Y. Wu, S. Liu, and M. C. Marchetti, Physicists discover new route to active matter self-organisation, *Nat. Phys.* **17**, 1037 (2021). doi:10.1038/s41567-021-01216-6
- [16] E. S. Gloag, M. A. Javed, H. Wang, M. L. Gee, S. A. Wade, L. Turnbull, and C. B. Whitchurch, Stigmergy: A key driver of self-organization in bacterial biofilms, *Commun. Integr. Biol.* **6**, e27331 (2013). doi:10.4161/cib.27331
- [17] H.-C. Flemming, J. Wingender, U. Szewzyk, P. Steinberg, S. A. Rice, and S. Kjelleberg, Biofilms: an emergent form of microbial life, *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* **14**, 563 (2016). doi:10.1038/nrmicro.2016.94
- [18] D. Tielker, S. Eichinger, S. Hacker, R. Loris, and P. Janning, The *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* lectin LecB is located in the outer membrane and is involved in biofilm formation, *Microbiology* **155**, 1308 (2009). doi:10.1099/mic.0.025453-0
- [19] P.-P. Grassé, La reconstruction du nid et les coordinations chez les termites, *Insectes Soc.* **6**, 41 (1959).
- [20] G. Theraulaz and E. Bonabeau, A brief history of stigmergy, *Artif. Life* **5**, 97 (1999). doi:10.1162/106454699568728
- [21] J. F. Benson and B. R. Patterson, Inter-specific territoriality in a *Canis* hybrid zone: Spatial segregation between wolves, coyotes, and hybrids, *Oecologia* **173**, 1539 (2013). doi:10.1007/s00442-013-2730-8
- [22] L. A. White, S. VandeWoude, and M. E. Craft, A mechanistic, stigmergy model of territory formation in solitary animals: Territorial behavior can dampen disease prevalence but increase persistence *PLoS Comput. Biol.* **16**, e1007457 (2020). doi:10.1371/journal.pcbi.1007457
- [23] J. R. Potts and M. A. Lewis, Territorial pattern formation in the absence of an attractive potential, *J. Math. Biol.* **72**, 25 (2016). doi:10.1007/s00285-015-0881-4
- [24] K. P. O’Keeffe, H. Hong, and S. H. Strogatz, Oscillators that sync and swarm, *Nat. Commun.* **8**, 1504 (2017). doi:10.1038/s41467-017-01190-3.
- [25] M. Hadeli, P. Valckenaers, M. Kollingbaum, and H. Van Brussel, Multi-agent coordination and control using stigmergy, *Comput.Ind.* **53**, 75 (2004). doi:10.1016/S0166-3615(03)00123-4
- [26] M. Salman, D. Garzón Ramos, and M. Birattari, Automatic design of stigmergy-based behaviours for robot swarms, *Commun. Eng.* **3**, 30 (2024). doi:10.1038/s44172-024-00175-7
- [27] R. Beckers, O. E. Holland, and J. L. Deneubourg, From local actions to global tasks: Stigmergy and collective robotics, in *Artificial Life IV: Proceedings of the Fourth International Workshop on the Synthesis and Simulation of Living Systems*, edited by C. G. Langton (MIT Press,

- 1994), pp. 181–189.
- [28] Q. Tang, Z. Xu, F. Yu, Z. Zhang, and J. Zhang, Dynamic target searching and tracking with swarm robots based on stigmergy mechanism, *Robot. Auton. Syst.* **120**, 103251 (2019). doi:10.1016/j.robot.2019.103251
 - [29] E. Ferrante, A. E. Turgut, E. A. Duéñez-Guzmán, and M. Dorigo, Testing the limits of pheromone stigmergy in high-density robot swarms, *R. Soc. Open Sci.* **6**, 190225 (2019). doi:10.1098/rsos.190225
 - [30] M. Schubotz, The role of stigmergy in decentralized systems for the Semantic Web, *J. Web Semant.* **70**, 32 (2022). doi:10.1016/j.websem.2022.02.005
 - [31] O. Witkowski and T. Ikegami, Emergence of Swarming Behavior: Foraging Agents Evolve Collective Motion Based on Signaling, *PLoS ONE* **11**, e0152756 (2016). doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0152756
 - [32] A. Lizarraga and M. A. M. de Aguiar, Synchronization and spatial pattern formation in swarmalator systems, *Phys. Rev. E* **102**, 052604 (2020). doi:10.1103/PhysRevE.102.052604
 - [33] M. S. Anwar, G. K. Sar, M. Perc, and D. Ghosh, Collective dynamics of swarmalators with higher-order interactions, *Commun. Phys.* **7**, 59 (2024). doi:10.1038/s42005-024-01556-2
 - [34] N. Blum, A. Li, K. O’Keeffe, and O. Kogan, Swarmalators with delayed interactions, *Phys. Rev. E* **109**, 014205 (2024). doi:10.1103/PhysRevE.109.014205
 - [35] S. Ceron, K. P. O’Keeffe, and K. Petersen, Diverse behaviors in non-uniform chiral and non-chiral swarmalators, *Nat. Commun.* **14**, 940 (2023). doi:10.1038/s41467-023-36563-4
 - [36] I. Lu, Y. Xu, W. Cai, Z. Tian, J. Xu, S. Wang, T. Zhu, Y. Liu, M. Wang, Y. Zhou, C. Yan, C. Li, and Z. Zheng, Self-organized circling, clustering and swarming in populations of chiral swarmalators, *Chaos Solitons Fractals* **191**, 115794 (2025). doi:10.1016/j.chaos.2024.115794
 - [37] G. K. Sar, D. Ghosh, and K. P. O’Keeffe, Pinning in a system of swarmalators, *Phys. Rev. E* **107**, 024215 (2023). doi:10.1103/PhysRevE.107.024215
 - [38] G. K. Sar, D. Ghosh, and K. P. O’Keeffe, Driven synchronization of swarmalators in a time-varying external field, *Phys. Rev. E* **109**, 044603 (2024). doi:10.1103/PhysRevE.109.044603
 - [39] B. Adorjáni, D. Ghosh, and K. P. O’Keeffe, Active particles under spatially varying friction, *Phys. Rev. E* **109**, 024607 (2024). doi:10.1103/PhysRevE.109.024607
 - [40] G. K. Sar, K. P. O’Keeffe, and D. Ghosh, Synchronization and spatial pattern formation in a ring of swarmalators with asymmetric nearest-neighbor coupling, *Phys. Rev. E* **111**, 024206 (2025). doi:10.1103/PhysRevE.111.024206
 - [41] K. P. O’Keeffe, S. Ceron, and K. Petersen, Collective behaviors of swarmalators in a periodic box, *Phys. Rev. E* **105**, 014211 (2022). doi:10.1103/PhysRevE.105.014211
 - [42] S. Yoon, J.-H. Hong, H. Hong, and S.-W. Son, Topological synchronization and pattern formation in swarmalators, *Phys. Rev. E* **106**, 054203 (2022). doi:10.1103/PhysRevE.106.054203
 - [43] X. Yang, M. L. Manning, and M. C. Marchetti, Aggregation and segregation of confined active particles, *Soft Matter* **10**, 6477 (2014). doi:10.1039/c4sm00927d
 - [44] G. Gonnella, D. Marenduzzo, A. Suma, and A. Tiribocchi, Motility-induced phase separation and coarsening in active matter, *C. R. Phys.* **16**, 316 (2015). doi:10.1016/j.crhy.2015.01.002
 - [45] A. Torres-Carbajal and F. J. Sevilla, Motility-induced phase separation of soft active Brownian particles, *Phys. Fluids* **36**, 027129 (2024). doi:10.1063/5.0185048

- [46] L. Caprini, M. L. Manganelli, M. Paoluzzi, and U. Marini Bettolo Marconi, Dynamical clustering and wetting phenomena in inertial active matter, *Commun. Phys.* **7**, 343 (2024). doi:10.1038/s42005-024-01835-y
- [47] C. Bettstetter, T. Schmickl, G. D. Tipaldi, W. Elmenreich, R. Groß, and A. Giuliani, Stochastic Swarmalators for Robotic Systems, *IEEE Robot. Autom. Lett.* **8**, 4221 (2023). doi:10.1109/LRA.2023.3268172
- [48] A. Font Llenas, M. Schmickl, T. Nakagaki, and H. Hamann, Stigmergic communication for self-organized robot swarms, *Swarm Intell.* **14**, 123 (2020). doi:10.1007/s11721-020-00185-z
- [49] F. Heylighen, Stigmergy as a paradigm for self-organization, *Cogn. Syst. Res.* **38**, 4 (2016). doi:10.1016/j.cogsys.2015.12.001
- [50] H. Hamann, *Swarm Robotics: A Formal Approach* (Springer, Cham, 2018). doi:10.1007/978-3-319-74315-4
- [51] C. D. Nadell, K. Drescher, and K. R. Foster, Spatial structure, cooperation and competition in biofilms, *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* **13**, 589 (2015). doi:10.1038/nrmicro3521
- [52] K. P. O’Keeffe, J. H. M. Evers, and T. Kolokolnikov, Traveling waves in swarmalator systems, *Phys. Rev. E* **98**, 022203 (2018). doi:10.1103/PhysRevE.98.022203
- [53] J. Bialké, T. Speck, and H. Löwen, Active Brownian particles: A model for self-propelled particles with persistence, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **108**, 168301 (2012). doi:10.1103/PhysRevLett.108.168301
- [54] J. Stenhammar, R. Wittkowski, D. Marenduzzo, and M. E. Cates, Continuum theory of active Brownian particles, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **111**, 145702 (2013). doi:10.1103/PhysRevLett.111.145702
- [55] A. Boldini, M. Civitella, and M. Porfiri, Stigmergy: from mathematical modelling to control, *R. Soc. Open Sci.* **11**, 240845 (2024). doi:10.1098/rsos.240845
- [56] M. Eguchi, M. Nishimura, S. Yoshida, and T. Hiraki, Robot Swarm Control Based on Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics for Obstacle-Unaware Navigation, in *Proc. IEEE/RSJ Int. Conf. Intell. Robots Syst. (IROS)*, 9006–9013 (2024). doi:10.1109/IROS58592.2024.10801800
- [57] G. Bánó, C. Slabý, A. Strejčková, Z. Tomori, A. Hovan, P. Miskovsky, and D. Horvath, Controlled stigmergy in quasi-one-dimensional active particle systems, *Phys. Rev. E* **110**, 024605 (2024). doi:10.1103/PhysRevE.110.024605
- [58] A. P. Antonov, L. Caprini, A. Ldov, C. Scholz, and H. Löwen, Inertial active matter with Coulomb friction, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **133**, 198301 (2024). doi:10.1103/PhysRevLett.133.198301

Supplemental Material for *Stigmergic Feedback in Swarmalator Mixtures: Phase-Mediated Segregation Under Confinement*

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To further illustrate the complex behavior of swarmalator mixtures, this supplemental material focuses on the diversity of emergent configurations. We achieve this by monitoring systemic nonequilibrium macrostates. The specific configurations observed are determined by key parameters including stigmergic coupling strength (K_{np}), angular rotation rate (ω_A), time horizons (t_H), boundary conditions, and barrier-influenced conditions (presence or absence of a barrier). These configurations are visualized to facilitate a comprehensive understanding of their spatial and temporal evolution.

To qualitatively assess the effects of these parameters, we developed a classification scheme to describe their macroscopic consequences. This parameter-based organization is designed to clarify the individual roles of each parameter in shaping structural integrity, spatial organization, and cluster maturation (sharpness) over t_H .

Our analysis begins with a qualitative characterization of the properties influencing parametric combinations, followed by a systematic summary of the observed non-equilibrium states across varying initial conditions.

We have organized our feature tracking into four problem categories, which are as follows:

1. Stigmergic coupling K_{np} as a determinant of structural integrity in swarmalator populations

- Weak coupling ($K_{np} = 0.1$):
 - Fluid-like boundaries: Clusters display low curvature, with density decreasing smoothly from the dense core to the sparse periphery.
 - Dynamic cluster behavior: Characterized by frequent cluster merging and splitting, along with high cluster mobility throughout the system.
- Strong coupling ($K_{np} = 0.4$): rigid, well-segregated structures
 - Formation and stabilization of structures: stable ring-shape morphology, aligned walls due to rotational motion.
 - Reduced mobility of clusters: significantly decreased translational motion.
 - Coherence in rotation: Homogeneous clusters of A or B type are formed.

2. Angular velocity (ω_A) governs spatial organization defined by the r_p length scale

- Low angular velocity ($\omega_A = 0.1$): boundary-dominated organization
 - Boundary-induced deformations: swarmalators collide with boundaries, and cluster shapes are altered by the boundaries.
 - Boundary wetting in swarmalators: tendency of swarmalators to accumulate or spread along boundaries.
- High angular velocity ($\omega_A \geq 0.2$): isolation of clusters
 - Sharper and well-defined cluster interfaces.

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- Compact cluster shapes: Clusters exhibit a tendency to retract protrusions and become more cohesive.
- Structural stability: Clusters maintain their structural integrity across pre-collisional and post-collisional states, demonstrating resilience to perturbative interactions.

3. Temporal evolution and cluster maturation influenced by t_H values

- Early horizon ($t_H = 2 \times 10^5$): initial cluster formation
 - Incomplete cohesion: clusters are partially formed; not all swarmalators are incorporated.
 - High swarmalator isolation: A significant number of swarmalators remain unclustered.
- Intermediate horizon ($t_H = 4 \times 10^5$): dense packing
 - Tighter packing: Swarmalators become more densely packed within clusters.
 - Reduced individual mobility: individual mobility of swarmalators decreases.
- Late horizon ($t_H = 2 \times 10^6$): structural changes approaching freeze
 - Complete incorporation: Nearly all swarmalators are fully integrated into clusters.
 - Smoother interfaces: Cluster boundaries become sharper due to rotational alignment.
 - Morphology: Transient protrusions and unstable features dissipate, leading to structurally metastable configurations.

4. Boundary effects, confinement as morphological filter

- $L_{bar} = 0$
 - Isotropic behavior: Swarmalators tend to segregate largely by chance.
 - Wetting dynamics: Swarmalators move with minimal spatial constraints.
- $L_{bar} = L/2$ - bulk guided self-organization
 - Channelled movement: swarmalators exhibit directed motion.
 - Remodeling and pinning of clusters: occur via interactions with barrier.
 - Modified wetting behavior: wetting flow altered.
 - Enhanced cluster purity: stabilization of cluster morphologies.

The following pages present non-equilibrium configuration snapshots, evolved from randomly generated configurations, for $N = 200$ swarmalators (types A and B). Each page displays sixteen configurations, with each configuration corresponding to specific parameters. These are divided into two categories: 8 barrier-free configurations (Conf. (without barrier) No. 1 – No. 8) and 8 configurations with barrier-influenced boundary conditions barriers (Conf. (with barrier) No. 1 – No. 8).

Using parameters $K_{np} = 0.1$, $\omega_A = 0.1$, and a short horizon $t_H = 2 \times 10^5$, we captured two sets of snapshots. The top 8 configurations show the system without a barrier, while the bottom 8 configurations depict the system with a barrier in place. The same structure is maintained in the following pages.

Parameters: $K_{np} = 0.1, \omega_A = 0.2, t_H = 2 \times 10^5$ (short horizon).

Parameters: $K_{np} = 0.1, \omega_A = 0.4, t_H = 2 \times 10^5$ (short horizon).

Parameters: $K_{np} = 0.4$, $\omega_A = 0.1$, $t_H = 2 \times 10^5$ (short horizon). Note: At the corners and edges, both wetting (see Conf. (without barrier) No.3, 4, 7, 8) and boiling (see Conf. (without barrier) No.1, 3, 6, 8) occur, alongside the effects observed with the barrier (see Conf. (with barrier) No.2–8). These phenomena are coupled with the collision of ring-shaped clusters, where reflective boundaries play a significant role in shaping the resulting behaviors.

Parameters: $K_{np} = 0.4, \omega_A = 0.2, t_H = 2 \times 10^5$ (short horizon). Note: The interaction between clusters results in mutual deformation, while the barrier introduces additional deformation, as shown in Configuration (with barrier) No.2. Wetting can occur despite the presence of the barrier, as illustrated in Configuration (with barrier) No.6.

Parameters: $K_{np} = 0.4, \omega_A = 0.3, t_H = 2 \times 10^5$ (short horizon). Note: Boiling of sw

Parameters: $K_{np} = 0.4, \omega_A = 0.4, t_H = 2 \times 10^5$ (short horizon).

Parameters: $K_{np} = 0.1, \omega_A = 0.1, t_H = 4 \times 10^5$ (middle horizon). For higher horizons ($t_H = 4 \times 10^5$), the contours of large rings become clearer, yet paradoxically, the barriers exhibit a disruptive effect.

Parameters: $K_{np} = 0.1, \omega_A = 0.2, t_H = 4 \times 10^5$ (middle horizon). Note: Clusters exhibit exceptional size diversity due to the dominant mechanism of 'motility-induced separation and coarsening.' The presence of a barrier does not seem to affect key system statistics.

Parameters: $K_{np} = 0.1, \omega_A = 0.3, t_H = 4 \times 10^5$ (middle horizon).

Parameters: $K_{np} = 0.1, \omega_A = 0.4, t_H = 4 \times 10^5$ (middle horizon).

Parameters: $K_{np} = 0.4, \omega_A = 0.1, t_H = 4 \times 10^5$ (middle horizon). Note: The results show a pronounced dependence on whether a barrier is present.

Parameters: $K_{np} = 0.4, \omega_A = 0.2, t_H = 4 \times 10^5$ (middle horizon).

Parameters: $K_{np} = 0.4, \omega_A = 0.3, t_H = 4 \times 10^5$ (middle horizon).

Parameters: $K_{np} = 0.4, \omega_A = 0.4, t_H = 4 \times 10^5$ (middle horizon).

Parameters: $K_{np} = 0.1, \omega_A = 0.1, t_H = 2 \times 10^6$ (long horizon).

Parameters: $K_{np} = 0.1, \omega_A = 0.2, t_H = 2 \times 10^6$ (long horizon).

Parameters: $K_{np} = 0.1, \omega_A = 0.3, t_H = 2 \times 10^6$ (long horizon).

Parameters: $K_{np} = 0.1, \omega_A = 0.4, t_H = 2 \times 10^6$ (long horizon).

Parameters: $K_{np} = 0.4, \omega_A = 0.1, t_H = 2 \times 10^6$ (long horizon).

Parameters: $K_{np} = 0.4, \omega_A = 0.2, t_H = 2 \times 10^6$ (long horizon).

Parameters: $K_{np} = 0.4, \omega_A = 0.3, t_H = 2 \times 10^6$ (long horizon).

Parameters: $K_{np} = 0.4, \omega_A = 0.4, t_H = 2 \times 10^6$ (long horizon).

